

Supplemental figures

Respiratory rhythm modulates membrane potential and spiking of non-olfactory neurons

Maxime Juventin¹, Mickael Zbili^{1,2}, Nicolas Fourcaud-Trocmé¹, Samuel Garcia¹, Nathalie Buonviso¹ and Corine Amat^{1*}

¹ Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, CNRS, INSERM, Centre de Recherche en Neurosciences de Lyon CRNL U1028 UMR5292, F-69500, Bron, France

² Université Clermont Auvergne, CHU Clermont-Ferrand, INSERM, Neuro-Dol, F-63100, Clermont-Ferrand, France

Journal of Neurophysiology

Number of figures = 6

S1: Input resistance

Characterization of neuron input resistance. Input resistance distribution. (mean = $52.7 \pm 4.7\text{M}\Omega$).

S2: Polarity states

Verification of the encoding of the polarity. Each point corresponds to a cell. **A)** Distribution of injected currents. **B)** Distribution of normalized rest membrane potential (RMP). Rest membrane potential was estimated from the median membrane potential. Normalization consisted in subtracting the RMP of the polarity of interest from that of the base. **C)** Distribution of normalized firing rate. Normalization consisted in subtracting the firing rate of the polarity of interest from that of the base. **D)** Dimensional reduction with the t-SNE (t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding) algorithm. A vector composed of the injected currents (panel A), normalized RMP (panel B) and normalized firing rate (panel C) was subjected to the t-SNE algorithm. Colors are from our manual encoding. Basal, depolarized and hyperpolarized levels are well separated. Hyper1 and Hyper2, on the other hand, overlap.

S3: AP waveform

Action potential duration is homogeneous. **A)** Action potential waveform. For each neuron, all action potentials have been normalized by their amplitude and averaged. Average waveforms are plotted. The inset is a zoom out. **B)** Half-width distribution of the average waveforms shown in A. mean = 1.07 ± 0.02 ms

S4: Verification of possible correlations

Control of parameters influencing RRo probability. Each point corresponds to a cell. **A)** Correlation between RRo probability and recording duration (measured in number of respiratory cycles). Recording duration does not bias RRo detection ($pv = 0.28$). **B)** Correlation between RRo probability and mean respiratory frequency. Mean respiratory frequency is a proxy for depth of anesthesia. No correlation was observed ($pv = 0.99$); **C)** Correlation between RRo probability and input resistance. For measurement of input resistance, see Figure Supplemental S4. No correlation was observed ($pv = 0.8$). **D)** Correlation between RRo probability and coherence in respiratory band. Coherence between membrane potential and respiration was computed, and we averaged the coherence values in the respiratory frequency band (respiratory frequency ± 0.3 Hz). A significant correlation was observed ($pv = 5.6 \cdot 10^{-16}$).

S5: Effect of excitability changes

Internal excitability level has little influence on the percentage of respiration-coupled cells on the overall population, but hyperpolarization decreases the percentage of RRo MP cycles in a cell-by-cell analysis. Data from mPFC, S1 and HPC have been pooled. A) Percentage of cells modulated by respiration as a function of internal excitability states. Numbers of cells appear in each black bar. **B)** Evolution of the MP RRo probability, for individual cells, between hyper1 and base states. Only cells recorded in hyper1 and base conditions are shown. Recordings must be close in time (3.5 ± 0.7 min, see methods) (Wilcoxon paired test, $p = 0.01$, statistic value = 7, $N = 16$).

S6: Obstruction of the nostril

Nostril reopening simultaneously triggers RRo in membrane potential of mPFC cell and LFP. **A)** Morlet wavelet time-frequency plots. The upper plot corresponds to membrane potential and the lower plot to LFP. Instantaneous respiratory frequency is highlighted by the red dotted curves. From 0 to 4s, the nostril is clogged. Nostril is open at 4s. **B** Raw traces. The upper trace corresponds to membrane potential, the middle to respiratory signal and the lower to LFP. **C** Respiration-triggered average plots. Plots were made before opening (0 to 4s), just after opening (4 to 8s) and later (8 to 12s). Black traces correspond to the median. Grey shading corresponds to 5th and 95th percentiles.